

The Impact of UKRI Research Councils Funded Research on Policy: An Explorative Analysis.

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Abstract: This study explores how research funded by the seven UKRI Research Councils from 2012 to 2022 has influenced policy development. It investigates 1) the extent of funded research cited in policies, 2) the benefiting organisations, 3) the policy topics most influenced, and 4) whether highly cited academic papers have a greater policy impact. Publications from the Web of Science associated with each council were cross-referenced against the Overton policy database to identify research cited in policies. The Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC) demonstrated the highest policy impact, with 39.6% of its funded publications cited in policies. In contrast, research funded by the Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC) had the lowest policy citation rate of 0.8%. Government policies were the most frequent beneficiaries of funded research, comprising 51.7% of all cited publications across councils. Analysis of policy topics revealed alignments with each council's disciplinary focus; strikingly, documents cited in policies tended to be highly cited in their academic field, with a significant portion ranking in the top 10% field citation percentile, suggesting policymakers may preferentially rely on highly cited research. These results provide initial insights into the interplay between funded research and policy outcomes. Quantifying citations in policy is valuable, but this alone may inadequately capture societal impact across all disciplines. Further investigation is needed to deepen the understanding of evidence-based policymaking and measures of societal benefit from research.

Introduction

UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) is a non-departmental organisation crucial in funding research activities in the United Kingdom. It was established in 2018, bringing together seven previously independent research councils (RCUK), along with Innovate UK and Research England. The organisation aims to foster a dynamic and competitive research environment, nurture talent, and drive economic growth through the development and commercialisation of cutting-edge technologies and ideas.

Every year UKRI invest a healthy budget in research initiatives. In March 2022, UKRI confirmed a budget allocation for the financial years 2022-23 to 2024-25 of £25.1 billion², making it one of the largest public funding bodies for research and innovation globally.

Due to the substantial investment from taxpayers, UKRI bears the responsibility to demonstrate how funded projects benefit society by delivering a clear societal return. This is exemplified through yearly reports detailing expenditures and showcasing added value. One of the strategic aims often emphasised in these reports is the ability to drive policy practice and improvements. Consequently,

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² [UKRI-241023-BudgetAllocationExplainer2022To2025.pdf](#)

the distribution of research funding to some extent reflects researchers' capacity to achieve 'societal impact'.

Achieving societal impact has relevance also outside UKRI: the UK 'impact agenda' was initiated with REF2014 (Boswell and Smith, 2017), and since then, the importance of quantifying 'impact' has increased to a point where it has been estimated that in the upcoming REF (2029), a high-quality impact study could be worth £250K per year, compared to a 4-star paper valued at £10K per year³. As a consequence, UK universities rely heavily on public funds to drive projects that yield both scholarly and societal returns.

As if that were not enough, there is a collective pressure, partly driven by the Open Science movement, aiming to break the 'ivory tower' of science by making knowledge as widely accessible as possible, which subjects science to even larger scrutiny. As a result, researchers now more than ever need to explain the non-academic value of their work, demonstrating that their activities align with the public interest (Boswell and Smith, 2017; Smith and Steward, 2016).

The use of research in policies is considered one effective approach to quantify knowledge exchange from research to the community and probably one of the most direct ways for research findings to improve the quality of life. Grimshaw *et al.* (2012), for example, discuss how the failure to translate findings from clinical research into policy results in poorer quality of life, exposing patients to unnecessary risks and the healthcare systems to unnecessary expenditure. Thus, underlining the importance of tracking research use in policymaking.

However, quantifying the relationship between research and policy is a rather challenging issue and various studies attempted to theoretically analyse the reasons why research may or may not be used in policy (Dunn, 1980; Stone, 2002; Hassell, 2015; Boswell and Smith, 2017; Yin *et al.*, 2021).

This study proposes an explorative analysis of how research funded from 2012 to 2022 by the seven UKRI Research Councils has influenced policy development. It seeks to understand the (i) extent of funded research used in policy, (ii) the types of policies benefitting most, (iii) which policy topics are the most influenced by research, and (iv) investigates whether academic citations influence policy use. In the final section a comparison between Web of Science and Overton databases to harvest data on funded publications cited in policies is also proposed.

This analysis doesn't claim to be an exhaustive investigation of the interplay between research and policy, but it rather aims to be a preliminary investigation to further understand whether citation in policy can be used as an indicator for the 'societal impact' sought by UKRI, REF and other funding bodies.

The seven Research Councils cover all disciplines and are organised as follows:

- *Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC)* funds research across the whole range of the Arts and Humanities.
- *Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BBSRC)* funds research focused on biology and health disciplines.
- *Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC)* is the funder of economic, social and behavioural data sciences.

³ <https://www.researchprofessionalnews.com/rr-news-uk-views-of-the-uk-2023-6-ref-2028-impact-becomes-more-valuable/>

- 4. *Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC)* focus on engineering and physical sciences.
- 5. *Medical Research Council (MRC)* funds medical research on illness prevention and therapies.
- 6. *Natural Environment Research Council (NERC)* funds environmental related research.
- 7. *Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC)* supports astronomy, physics and space science.

In this study, *citation in policy documents* is used as the metric to measure use in policy documents, with data on policies retrieved from Overton, the world's largest searchable policy database. It indexes around 12 million policy documents and over 5 million scholarly publications cited in policy and maps them into DOI. Overton started in 2019 and collects policy as far back as it can; However, the search for policy documents before 2015 may be less precise, as some of these documents might have been lost due to the closure or merging of government agencies.

Overton defines policy as "*documents written primarily for or by policymakers that are published by a policy-focused source*"; in this work, the same definition of policy document is adopted throughout.

Disclaimer: This study does not presume that research contributing to policy has a superior societal value compared to other research. Research across all fields contributes to enhancing everyday life, ranging from practical applications to theoretical studies aimed at bridging knowledge gaps. This study aims to explore one avenue for measuring the impact of research on society.

1. How much of the research funded by the Research Councils is cited in policy?

This first question aims to analyse the use of the Research Councils' funded research in policy development, focusing on publications between 2012 to 2022.

I used the "Analyze – Funder" module of *InCites* – Clarivate analytical tool which uses data from the Web of Science (WoS) Core Collection - to identify publications associated with the seven UKRI Research Councils. I downloaded the publication list for each Research Council in Excel spreadsheets and excluded from those lists the documents without a DOI. The resulting DOI lists were then used to cross-reference publications with the Overton database to determine the extent to which they are cited in policy documents. To do so, I conducted a "Scholarly Articles" search on Overton using DOIs. I saved the documents returned from the Overton search for each Research Council and used those for all the analyses carried out in this study. Rstudio – ggplot package- was used to create all images.

Results:

Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) and Medical Research Council (MRC) emerged as the most prolific councils, with both producing well over 100,000 publications in ten years (Table 1).

Table 1 Number of Web of Science documents per Council cited in policies and citing policies.

Research Council	WoS documents	WoS Documents with DOI	WoS Documents cited in policy	Policies citing WoS documents
AHRC	9,945	9,476	948	2,149
BBSRC	62,061	61,303	6,019	9,492
EPSRC	175,638	166,088	7,968	17,826
ESRC	39,826	39,038	15,463	74,461
MRC	134,322	130,815	23,846	56,862
NERC	49,914	49,443	12,540	24,354
SFTC	45,556	45,124	381	682

Figure 1 Percentage of WoS documents per Research Council published between 2012 and 2022 cited in policy documents.

Despite lower publication volumes, the Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC) is revealed as the council with the most significant impact on policy shaping. As shown in Figure 1, 39.6% of research funded by ESRC is cited in policy documents, making ESRC-funded publications the most used in policy discussions. This is followed by the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC) at 25.4% and the Medical Research Council (MRC) at 18.2%. In contrast, Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) and the Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC) contribute the least to policy discussions (respectively 4.8% and 0.8%)(Fig.1). Looking at the number of policies citing funded research (Table 1, Fig.2), on average each article across all councils has contributed to more than one policy ($M=2.43$, $Sd= 1.09$). ESRC publications contributed to a staggering 74,461 policy documents, which indicates that each ESRC article was used in 4.8 policies. The citing policy count excludes multiple citations within the same document but considers translations into different languages as separate documents.

Figure 2 Number of WoS documents cited in policies and citing policies per Research Council.

2. Which Organisation benefits the most from funded research?

Using the list of WoS documents found on Overton as described above, I proceeded to analyse the organisations that cite Research Councils' funded research.

I gained the figures used in this analysis from the Overton filter for 'Policy Type'. Overton's categorisation system comprehends three primary policy categories according to the source the policy is obtained from:

- Government: Policies sourced from governmental agencies.
- IGO (International Governmental Organisations): Policies sourced from international agencies dealing with issues spanning multiple nations and aimed at addressing global challenges, such as the United Nations.
- Think Tank: Policies sourced from policy institutes, typically non-governmental organisations.

Documents meeting Overton's policy definition but sourced from entities other than those mentioned above are classified as "other". Overton doesn't currently disambiguate across policy sources and the same document can appear twice as long as two different organisations host it in different places⁴. Because the category 'other' includes data sourced from aggregators, i.e. websites that collect documents from other sources and put them in one place for easier access, I excluded it from the analysis to minimise policy duplication.

Results:

Notably, publications funded by all Research Councils contribute to each of these policy categories (Table 2; Figure 3). Among these, governmental agencies stand out as the ones using the highest proportion of funded research publications for policy development, citing 51.7% of the total cited

⁴ <https://help.overton.io/article/how-we-disambiguate-policy-documents/>

Table 2. Proportion of funded research documents cited in different policy types. The percentages are calculated over the total of the publications used in the three policy categories considered per Council.

Research Council	Government		IGO		Think Tank	
	N Doc	%	N Doc	%	N Doc	%
AHRC	776	46.6	342	20.5	547	32.9
BBSRC	6367	56.6	2151	19.12	2732	24.3
EPSRC	8661	54.8	3216	20.4	3915	24.8
ESRC	15479	40.9	8749	23.11	13630	36.0
MRC	28996	60.3	11302	23.48	7822	16.3
NERC	12130	47.0	7772	30.1	5948	23.0
STFC	291	64.0	75	16.5	89	19.6

Figure 3 The flow of the Research Councils' funded research into different policy types.

publications across councils. STFC and MRC are the councils whose research is mostly used in government policies, respectively 64 and 60.3%; while NERC research is the one that contributes the most to IGO policies. ESRC has a more balanced use across organisations; it is interesting to notice that the number of policies per organisation sums up to 37,878, which is a quite lower figure than the total number of citing policies found in point 1. This might indicate that ESRC research is employed in a wider spectrum of policies than the 3 represented by these categories.

3. Which Policy Areas benefit the most from funded research?

This analysis aims to shed light on the impact of funded research on various policy domains and it seeks to investigate whether the objectives of each council are mirrored in the policy areas influenced by their research.

To accomplish this, I once again used the list of Web of Science documents cited in policy for each council, and I used the classification provided by Overton to investigate the citing policies' subject areas. Overton provides two distinct policy classifications according to topics:

- Topics of Citing Policy: This offers a more detailed breakdown of policy documents, extracting the main themes from them.
- Classification of Citing Policy: This is a broader categorisation which indicates the general area in which the policy falls (e.g. science and technology).

For this analysis, I used the 'Topics of Citing Policy' classification to gain a more precise understanding of the policy topics influenced by funded research. Figure 4 summarises the top 10 citing policy topics for each Research Council, with categories containing fewer than 300 documents excluded for clarity. These are detailed in Table 3 for reference.

Figure 4. Distribution of funded publications per Research Council across the most frequent citing policy topics

Table 2 Top 10 policy topics citing STFC funded research.

Research Council	Policy topic	Count
STFC	Physical sciences	207
STFC	Nature	187
STFC	Applied interdisciplinary physics	153
STFC	Physics	150
STFC	Science	148
STFC	Research	110
STFC	Water	109
STFC	Astronomy	98
STFC	Space science	97
STFC	Technology	93

Results:

Overall, the data suggest a promising alignment between each council's focus and the policy areas influenced by their funded research. The Natural Environment Research Council prominently features in policies related to environmental and climate change issues, aligning with its focus. Similarly, the Medical Research Council is well-represented in medical and disease-related topics, as expected.

The Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council demonstrates influence in both health and biological topics, while the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council extends its impact from technology to environmental policy realms. In the social sciences, the Arts and Humanities Research Council and the Economic and Social Research Council show influence in areas such as education, poverty, and human activities. The Science and Technology Facilities Council stands out for its well-defined impact on planetary science and technology topics.

Notably, three policy topics—Health, Risk, and Research—emerge as focal points drawing expertise from multiple councils.

4. Is research cited in policy highly cited in the academic context?

This question aims to investigate the citation patterns of documents used in policies, to determine whether these documents tend to be highly cited papers in their respective academic fields.

I used the field citation percentile (FCP) as a metric to assess the citation impact of articles. This is a normalised measure that considers the year and field of publication when ranking documents. Papers ranked in the top 10% field citation percentile are considered highly cited in their respective fields.

I retrieved the field citation percentile of the funded documents cited in policies from the original lists obtained from *InCites* using Excel's VLOOKUP function. R was used to create FCP density distribution plots for each Research Council (Figure 5).

Results:

Figure 5 shows that the document percentile distribution across all Councils is highly skewed to the left, strongly suggesting that a significant portion of articles cited in policy are indeed highly cited in their respective fields, while poorly cited articles have a lower impact on policymaking.

Table 4 shows the percentage of funded articles cited in policy that rank in the top 10% FCP, alongside the percentage of all funded articles by each council ranked in the top 10% FCP. Remarkably, the percentage of highly cited articles is significantly higher among the group of documents cited in policies ($t = 13.636$, $df = 11.624$, $p < 0.05$).

The findings suggest two potential implications:

- **Alignment of Interests:** the use of highly cited papers in policy documents might indicate that policymakers' interests are aligned with academic interests.
- **Citation bias:** Policymakers' reliance on highly cited papers may be due to considering a high number of field-related citations as an endorsement of research credibility. This implies that the academic community's interests guide policymakers in selecting sources for policy development.

However, from this investigation, it is not possible to establish which one is the most plausible answer.

Table 3 Percentage of funded articles in the top 10% FCP cited in policy in comparison with the percentage of funded articles in the top 10% per Research Council.

<i>Research Council</i>	<i>% Documents cited in policy in top 10% FCP</i>	<i>% Funded Documents in top 10% FCP</i>
<i>AHRC</i>	48.52	27.15
<i>BBSRC</i>	46.28	21.68
<i>EPSRC</i>	44.09	18.67
<i>ESRC</i>	41.12	26.49
<i>MRC</i>	45.64	25.24
<i>NERC</i>	42.6	22.87
<i>STFC</i>	48.03	19.84

Figure 5 Distribution of funded publications cited in policy according to FCP. On the x-axis, 100 corresponds to the top 1 FCP and 90 equals to the top 10%.

5. Comparison of Web of Science and Overton Databases

Overton allows to search for research cited in policy funded by various funders, using built-in filters. Thus, it is possible to repeat the analysis I carried out using solely the Overton database. In this final section, I explored how WoS and Overton databases compare.

I first conducted a search in the ‘Scholarly Articles’ section of Overton using filters to identify research published between 2012 and 2022 funded by each UKRI Research Council. When using the ‘funder filter’ in Overton to select a specific funder, multiple options appear based on the source Overton is using to collect policy information. To maintain consistency when collecting data for this study, I entered the acronym of each council in the funder search box and selected all available options.

I downloaded the results on Excel spreadsheets, then I compared the DOIs retrieved from this search with the DOIs previously obtained (Web of Science documents found in Overton, as for section 1). This comparison was achieved by identifying unique DOIs between the lists of the two databases using conditional formatting and the COUNTIF function in Excel.

Results:

Overall, the publications found in Web of Science and from Overton databases overlap for 67.5%, ranging from 51 to 77% depending on the Research Council. The findings are summarised in Table 5 and Figure 6.

Figure 6 Comparison of research Councils funded publications cited in policy retrieved from WoS and Overton databases. In Lilac (Overlapping) are the articles present in both databases. In green are the articles unique to Overton and in orange are the ones unique to WoS.

Table 4 Proportion of Research Councils funded documents present in both databases (Overlap), and unique to the databases.

Research Council	% Overlap	% WoS unique	% Overton unique
AHRC	64.70	26.98	8.32
BBSRC	74.45	11.91	13.64
EPSRC	66.41	26.27	7.32
ESRC	51.06	32.10	16.84
MRC	74.50	18.90	6.60
NERC	73.40	22.98	3.61
SFTC	77.25	18.00	4.75

While this study did not delve deeply into the nuances of these discrepancies, a closer look at some DOIs provided insights into potential reasons:

- **Limitation in WoS Coverage:** Some DOIs of publications indexed in Overton are not present in the Web of Science database. The lower overlap, particularly noticeable for AHRC and ESRC, can be attributed to these subject areas being historically less represented in Web of Science.
- **Lack of Standardisation:** a significant issue seems to be caused by inconsistency in acknowledging funders in articles, quality of metadata, or database metadata harvesting capabilities. For instance, some articles classified under a specific Research Council in Web of

Science were found to be categorised under UKRI in Overton or not assigned to any funder at all. Such discrepancies contribute to differences in data collection.

- Search Methodology: The multiple options when filtering for a research council in Overton can be confusing. The approach used in this study might have led to some documents being missed, due to being categorised under a different funder nomenclature in the filter.

Summary of Findings and Discussion

This explorative study provides an initial look into the impact of research funded from 2012 to 2022 by the seven UKRI Research Councils on policy development. The questions addressed provide insights into the interplay between funded research and policy outcomes.

- 1) The study revealed that ESRC is the council with the highest impact on policy, with 39.6% of its funded research cited in policy documents. This finding aligns with the long-standing interest, dating back to 1978 (Weiss, 1978), in understanding how social sciences research shapes policy. Weiss (1978) elucidated how social sciences, by their very nature, can profoundly influence societal thinking, helping to define which problems should or should not be addressed by policy. More than 30 years later, the results of this study support the notion that research in the social sciences indeed holds a substantial influence on policy. On the other end, EPSRC and STFC had the lowest impact on policy, with respectively 4.8 and 0.8% of their funded research cited in policy documents. This does not diminish the societal impact of these councils' research; rather, it suggests that using policy citations as a metric may not adequately assess societal return for these disciplines.
- 2) Government policies emerged as the most frequent beneficiaries of funded research, comprising 51.7% of all cited publications across councils. This highlights that funded research plays a significant role in the development of policies directly impacting the society that funds it. Additionally, funded research was also used in IGOs, demonstrating that the impact extends beyond national boundaries and contributes to solving global challenges.
- 3) Clear alignments were observed across policy topics and the council's funded research focus, indicating that UKRI Research Councils maintained a clearly defined scope during the observed 10-year period, ensuring minimal overlap between agendas. However, the recent emphasis on "interdisciplinary" approaches in academia, highlighted in REF2029 and the proposal of THE (Times Higher Education) to create yet another ranking based on interdisciplinarity⁵ is prompting a reassessment of collaborative research practices within and across universities. This emerging agenda has the potential to blur the traditional "field boundaries" identified in this study. It would be intriguing to revisit this analysis in a decade to evaluate its impact on research focus areas and to observe potential refinements in these definitions. In addition, a more in-depth analysis, such as examining whether the subject areas of individual papers impact corresponding citing policy areas, is necessary to uncover additional insights into how research flows into policy. A limitation of this type of investigation is the lack of standardisation in research area categorisation across databases, which might lead to substantial differences in the results according to the classification used. Nonetheless, this is a topic that warrants further exploration.

⁵ <https://www.timeshighereducation.com/world-university-rankings/survey-first-interdisciplinary-science-rankings-now-open>),

- 4) An analysis of Field Citation Percentiles (FCP) indicated that a substantial portion of articles cited in policies rank in the top 10% of their respective fields. This suggests that policymakers often rely on highly cited papers for policy development. Similar findings were reported by Yin *et al.*, 2021, who conducted an extensive analysis of research impact on policy development and found that highly cited documents have a higher likelihood of being used in policy and media news. While this could indicate aligned interests among the public, policymakers, and academics (Yin *et al.*, 2021), it could also suggest that independent academic interests influence the selection of research for policy development, supporting the ‘supply’ model of research policy relations (Boswell and Smith, 2017). While it's challenging to determine the most plausible explanation solely from the data, citations seem to serve as indicators of the probability of being cited in policy.
- 5) Finally, the comparison between databases highlighted an issue that requires further investigation: the lack of standardisation in acknowledging funding in articles and the subsequent quality of metadata. More accurate and reliable data across databases will increase reproducibility and allow for more robust results.

In conclusion, this study provides preliminary insights into how research funded by UKRI Research Councils influences policy development at different levels. There is no indication or a set threshold to establish how much research used in policy is considered ‘good enough’ as societal return, and we observed that this varies significantly across fields. While the use of research in policy appears to be a constructive indicator for impact in social and environmental science, this may not be true in other domains. This difference across areas should be taken into consideration when evaluating ‘impact’ in research assessment exercises.

Further research in this area holds the potential to enhance our understanding of the intricate relationship between research, policy, and societal impact, leading to a deeper understanding of the dynamics contributing to evidence-based policymaking and the development of more robust measures for societal benefit.

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Data availability statement: data used in the study are available on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11280149>). The data used represents a snapshot in time. Recognising that new articles and policies are published and cited every day, it is not guaranteed that by replicating the methodology of this study the same results will be obtained.

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